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**“PARADIGM SHIFT IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN PRESENT
SCENARIO - EMERGING TRENDS”**

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ABSTRACT

In the 21st century where a man has become a resource, there is a paradigm shift in the trends in Human Resource Management. A look at the trends in managing people in this dynamic industry reflects that Attracting, Managing, Nurturing talent and Retaining people has emerged to be the single most critical issue in lieu of the enormous opportunities spun off by the market. New paradigms emerge as a result and new rules of the game have to be re-invented. Humankind then becomes the subjective and the objective force for all progress. The traditional HR only developed the policies of the organization. The present HR had to focus on employee growth, and had to be responsive to his needs and act as a bridge between the employers and the employee. The role of the HR has become very challenging, in this present scenario. They have to play a role in talent engagement, talent enhancement and talent retention. In fact, HR is no longer a function. It is a strategic partner in adding value; in several ways. The present paper tries to explore the emerging trends in HR field in the present scenario. The paper highlights the various challenges in changing business environment and presents strategies to make HRM effective in the present scenario to meet the global challenges.

Key Words: HR Practices, Managing People, Strategic Partner,

INTRODUCTION

“Man alone, of all the resources available to man, can grow and develop. The resources capable of enlargement can only be human resources”.

Peter. F. Drucker

Effective organizations are not build merely on investment and returns but more on the quality of the workforce, its commitment to the organizational goals and investments made to attract, train and retain superior human capital. Human Resources (HR) constitute the most valuable asset in the context of development. Relative performances of nations, of regions of economy, of sectors of industry as well as of corporate enterprises are critically linked to quality of human contribution. Even the gains from the intervention of superior technology in any field are closely related to its interface with human factor with corresponding skills as well as attitude. Owing to emergence of the global economy, over size capacity in many industries, ocean improvements in the power of computers and telecommunication tools, and the emergence of the knowledge economy are among the forces that are resulting in fundamental change in the design of HR arena of activities.

Human resource management is a process of bringing people and organizations together so that the goals of each other are met. The role of HR manager is shifting from that of a protector and screener to the role of a planner and change agent. Personnel directors are the new corporate heroes. The name of the game today in business is personnel. Nowadays it is not possible to show a good financial or operating report unless your personnel relations are in order. Over the years, highly skilled and knowledge based jobs are escalating while low skilled jobs are declining. This calls for future skill mapping through appropriate HRM initiatives. Indian organizations are also witnessing a change in systems, management cultures and philosophy due to the global alignment of Indian organizations. There is a need for multi skill development. Task of HRM is becoming all the more vital.

The degree to which HR function has undergone a change over the past decades gives the impression that; there is apparently no saturation point for the growth of the profession. Today, every additional person, with effective skills and competencies, means additional

profit. Earlier companies employed ‘hands.’ Obviously hands have limited productive potential. Today a company recruits people, it employs additional minds, and a creative mind has unlimited profit potential. Thus there is a qualitative difference in the field of HR between the industrial age and knowledge age. In industrial age HR was one of the numerous functions amongst manifold operations. In knowledge age, HR is at the heart of business. Every successful business leader in the knowledge age is a successful human resources manager.

A look at the trends in managing people in this dynamic industry reflects that Attracting, Managing, Nurturing talent and Retaining people has emerged to be the single most critical issue in lieu of the enormous opportunities spun off by the market. The new avatar of talent is the knowledge professional that is innovative, business savvy, quick on the uptake, has an instinctive ability to network, and possessing unbridled ambition. They are propelled by an urge to experiment, scan new avenues that can spur their creativity. The knowledge professional will gravitate to an organization that is flexible, has strong values, a robust performance ethic and provides challenging work on latest technology. This has led to companies proactively taking measures on three fronts. First, companies create an organizational ambience where talent can bloom. Second, they put in place systems that help unleash their potential and third, they build a reward and recognition mechanism that provides value for people

With the dynamic business scenario & the economic growth happening all around, a number of opportunities are emerging in India. The health of an organization depends more on its people / human resource & thus the role of HR has become ever so important.

There are three meanings attached to the concept of HRM:-

- In the first place, persons working in an organization are regarded as a valuable source, implying that there is a need to invest time and effort in their development;
- Secondly, they are human resources which mean that they have their own special characteristics and, therefore, cannot be treated like material resources. The approach focuses on the need to humanize organizational life and introduce human values in the organization; and

- Thirdly, human resources do not merely focus on employees as individuals, but also on other social realities, units and processes in the organization. These include the role or the job a person has in the organization, the dyadic unit, (consisting of the person and his superior), the various teams in which people work, inter-team processes, and the entity of the total organization.

There are some basic assumptions about human resources management. The important assumptions of HRM are as follows:

- The members of an organization are reservoirs of untapped resources.
- There is a scope for unlimited development of these resources.
- It is more in the nature of self-development than development thrust from outside.
- The organization also undergoes development with the overall benefits along with the development of its members.
- The organization further develops a culture in which utmost emphasis is placed on harmonious superior-subordinate relations, teamwork, collaboration among different groups of individuals, open communication, and above all, integration of the goals of the organization with the needs of the employees.
- Top management takes the initiative for HRM, formulates necessary plans and strategies, and creates an overall climate and support for its implementation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic.

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To examine challenges confronted the Human Resource Management;
- To find out the emerging trends in the field of Human Resource Management;
- To analyse the role of HR Manager in this context..

Area of Study

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of officers/managers of various companies in Jaipur and Moradabad district of Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh respectively, has been taken about the emerging trends and challenges faced in HR field. Their views have been incorporated in

this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on human resource management.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to implementation of HRM in various companies. Our focus group discussion was based on some companies in region of Jaipur and Moradabad districts. The discussions were based on key management initiatives with emphasis on HRM.. However, the names of companies have not been disclosed as per the request by the officials concerned.

PARADIGM SHIFT IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT - EMERGING TRENDS

The emerging trends in the field of HRM are described herein below:

- 1) **Open Work Environment:** Profound systemic changes have been seen in the way companies are structured. The concepts of leadership and managing people gave undergone a radical rethink. Cubicles, hierarchies and rigid organization structures of the past, have now given way to open work environment, flat structure with informality being a general rule and empowerment of individuals. Today work itself is centered around projects, which have virtual teams working on them. This work structure has led to a culture of flexi time and round the clock accessibility to the workplace.
- 2) **HRM as a Strategic Business Partner:** HRM business practice has evolved considerably over the years. The HRM is no longer viewed as an independent department that caters only to the needs of the employees but as business strategic partner. With this, more and more HRM functions are now being shared, if not delegated entirely, with line managers and supervisors. This is a welcome and advantageous development, not only for HR practitioners but for the organization as a whole. With these shared responsibilities, the HRM have now become an integral and indispensable part of organizational change, business planning, and development of company's competitiveness.
- 3) **Team Work:** The new economy has given rise to a culture of working in teams. Today no job in the knowledge industry can be performed in isolation. Since working in teams is not a passing fad, companies are now designing

- compensation structures, which reward team performance in addition to individual performance.
- 4) **Greater Emphasis on Talent Retention:** Companies have now started to develop psychological contracts / relations with their employees. “Service Bonds” are being gradually replaced by systems like “stock options”. This conveys the all important message of companies building up a permanent relationship with their employees. With this in mind companies are developing the vision / mission statements which indicate clearly the plans for the future. Company products are given to employees at greater discounts, scholarship given to their children, all in a bid to build up a lasting relationship and ensure that every employee feels proud to be part of the organisation.
 - 5) **Job Opportunities:** Comparing job opportunities that prevailed in the 1970’s and 1980’s and the opportunities available today we find that earlier, one had to wait for a job opening – just apply and wait. Now the scenario has changed - once a student has graduated, the job opportunities available to him/her are plenty. Some had even three or more job offers and found it difficult to make a choice.
 - 6) **Policies Become People Centric:** Traditionally the policies mainly focused on achievement of organizational goals showing negligence towards the human resource but now the policies of many companies have become people centric.
 - 7) **Impatient Youngsters:** At the entry level, there were many fresh candidates, but not enough quality. There is a need to match the skill and attitude of the employee, with the job on hand. There is need to match the demand and the supply. At the middle level, it is very difficult to meet the demand. In earlier days a person joined a company & stayed on – that would be his first & last job. Now youngsters are quite impatient & are constantly on the lookout for a change every two years, sometimes even earlier. There are many choices available for them. For the employee, the job is also choice driven.
 - 8) **Equitable Treatment of Employees:** In the Indian context, the good old adage was “All employees are equal but some are more equal than the others’. This meant that executives and senior managers were entitled to better facilities at the work place comfortable luxury transport to and from work, tea and coffee, a peon

at their disposal. With the increasing advent of open office systems, we notice that many organisations are heading for common canteens, pool cars and such. Further, with increased automation, executives are encouraged to have their own personal computers. Further we have tea-coffee vending machines with executives helping themselves to it as and when they need, self-operated photo coping machines. Thus, the hierarchical formal relationships at work are giving way for more informal and self-department ways of getting things done.

- 9) **Loyalty is Losing its Shine:** Attracting and retaining of human resource has become difficult as loyalty factor is losing its shine, today HR personnel have to motivate and design healthy career road map to make them stay in the company.
- 10) **Human Resource Outsourcing:** Human Resource Outsourcing is the new name in the industry to replace the redundant traditional HR department. Many HR outsourcing companies in India are already established and some are coming up to support increasing demand of corporate India.
- 11) **Quality Management:** The recent quality management standards ISO 9001 and ISO 9004 of 2000 focus more on people centric organizations. Organizations now need to prepare themselves in order to address people centered issues with commitment from the top management, with renewed thrust on HR issues, more particularly on training.
- 12) **Empowered Employee:** Today the employee is an empowered employee, who had many choices. He knew what is happening in the industry and he wanted the best. He wants better contracts and flexible timings and sometimes wants to work from home. Flexi-hours policy suits support functions that demand minimal.
- 13) **Flexi Work:** HR managers who favour working out of home say it reduces attrition and attracts quality workers. Flexi-work policy helps to convert commute time into productivity output, and to connect with people in areas where companies have no geographical presence. Companies feel virtual offices help in reducing certain fixed costs and office space per employee.
- 14) **Sensitivity Training:** Training and development extends beyond information and orientation training to include sensitivity training and field experiences that will

- enable the manager to understand cultural differences better. Managers need to be protected from career development risks, re-entry problems and culture shock.
- 15) **Quality of Work Life:** Organizations today are not only making the structure and policies employee friendly rather are trying to improve the quality of work life where employees can enjoy their working and will be able to manage the balance between work life and personal life. They provide them the in-house facility of health club, yoga, meditation, alternative work schedule, picnics, and family get together where they can reduce their stress and strains. They also provide educational facility, medical facility etc. Some companies also provide the employees holiday package along with their family members. The idea behind is not only to have a happy workforce but to get extended to the families of the employees as well to develop a sense of belongingness in the employees.
- 16) **Interest in Spirituality:** The biggest change in the workplace is the interest in spirituality. It's about doing the right thing. It's not about religion. It's about job satisfaction. Jobs in the future will have to be more meaningful. Pay won't be as important as a good job.
- 17) **Concept of Learning Organisation:** Training programmes are being viewed more seriously by organisations. Initially a training programme was perceived as a holiday period, break from routine work and a means to keep people occupied during preventive maintenance periods on the shop floor. Further training efforts of most organisations have been focused at the lower level of employees of the organisation. An encouraging trend today is that organisations are now emphasizing upon training of employees at all levels. Training and development activities are aimed at increasing "Learning" experiences for employees such that it helps in both employee and organisation development.

WHAT HR MANAGERS SHOULD DO

This new age economy, with its attendant paradigm shifts in relation to the human capital, in terms of its acquisition, utilization, development and retention, has placed a heavy demand on today's HR professionals. Today HR is expected to identify potential talent and also comprehend, conceptualize and implement relevant strategies to

contribute effectively to achieve organisational objectives. Hence a serious concern of every HR manager in order to survive this ‘War for Talent’, is to fight against a limited and diminishing pool of qualified available candidates to replace valuable employees when they leave, dramatically underscoring the difficulty to attract, motivate and retain the best employees in an organisation.

- 1) **Guiding Force to CEO:** It has been the busiest of times for any HR boss now, requiring him/her to do a tight rope walk. A talent manager, cost saver, trainer, mentor or even counselor to employees, an HR manager can be seen today, playing multiple roles that has made the position the next most influential person after the CEO. In times of crisis such as these days, the HR manager is an innovator and actually a guiding force for any CEO. Efficient manpower planning is the need of the hour and HR managers have to drive that change. HR managers have to be at the forefront of such changes in tow with business heads to help businesses. With companies struggling to keep their feet on ground in the financial turmoil, HR as a function has come a long way from being just a staff function to a key decision maker. And the meltdown has turned the pages deeper with HR and HR managers becoming an important aid in bailing out businesses.
- 2) **Use Workforce Skills:** Use workforce skills and abilities in order to exploit environmental opportunities and neutralize threats.
- 3) **Innovative Reward Plans:** Employ innovative reward plans that recognize employee contributions and grant enhancements.
- 4) **Quality Improvement:** Indulge in continuous quality improvement through TQM and HR contributions like training, development, counseling, etc
- 5) **Self Managed Teams:** Decentralize operations and rely on self-managed teams to deliver goods in difficult times e.g. Motorola is famous for short product development cycles. It has quickly commercialized ideas from its research labs.
- 6) **Lay off in a smooth way:** Lay off workers in a smooth way explaining facts to unions, workers and other affected groups e.g. IBM , Kodak, Xerox, etc.

DAVE ULRICH OUTLINES OLD MYTHS AND NEW REALITIES OF HR

Dave Ulrich outlines old myths and new realities of HR as following:

S.	Old Myths	New Realities of HR
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No.		
1	People go into HR because they like people	HR departments are not designed to provide corporate therapy or as social or health-and-happiness retreats. HR professionals must create the practices that make employees more competitive, not more comfortable.
2	Anyone can do HR.	HR activities are based on theory and research. HR professionals must master both theory and practice
3	HR deals with the soft side of a business and is therefore not accountable.	The impact of HR practices on business results can and must be measured. HR professionals must learn how to translate their work into financial performance.
4	HR focuses on costs, which must be controlled	HR practices must create value by increasing the intellectual capital within the firm. HR professionals must add value, not reduce costs.
5	HR's job is to be policy police and the health-and-happiness patrol.	The HR function does not own compliance-managers do. HR practices do not exist to make employees happy but to help them become committed. HR professionals must help managers commit employees and administer policies.
6	HR is full of fads	HR practices have evolved over time. HR professionals must see their current work as part of an evolutionary chain and explain their work with less jargon and more authority.
7	HR is staffed by nice people	At times, HR practices should force vigorous debates. HR professionals should be confrontative and challenging as well as supportive
8	HR is HR's job.	HR work is as important to line managers as are finance, strategy, and other business domains. HR professionals should join with managers in championing HR issues.

Finally, he writes that “the HR function traditionally has spent more time professing than being professional. The HR function has been plagued by myths that keep it from being professional. Regardless of whether these myths originate with HR people or with line managers, it is time they were overcome. It is time to talk less and do more; time to add value, not write value statements; time to build competitive, not comfortable, organizations; time to be proactive, not reactive. It is time to perform, not preach.”

CHALLENGES FACED BY HR MANAGER IN TODAY’S ENVIRONMENT

In the dynamic environment HR managers have to face lot of challenges. The important ones are:

- 1) **Change in Attitude:** The most challenging HR task is to bring about a change in attitude; to transform it from negative to positive, from suspicious to trusting, from domineering to motivating, from hierarchical to networking.
- 2) **Attrition:** Attrition is another major problem faced by the organizations today. To stop the cream from leaving the company, the HR has to take steps to satisfy the needs of the employees and improve their prospects within the organization.
- 3) **Need Levels of Employees:** At each stage the employees has certain needs. At the entry level they want rapid growth and earnings. At the middle level, they want challenge. At the senior level, they want to go higher up the ladder. The role of the HR has become very challenging, in this present scenario. They have to make the employee take an initiative to become leaders. They have to play a role in talent engagement, talent enhancement and talent retention.
- 4) **Hire Right Person:** Another great challenge for the HR in any organization is that the right person has to be hired. The employees, who performed well, have to be appreciated & acknowledged. Those who could improve on their performance have to be told to do so in a very nice manner.
- 5) **Work Ethics:** HR of today face challenges regarding ethics at workplace. In today’s world, the economy is vibrant and people have 3-4 job offers in hand, yet somewhere down the line, fundamental values are forgotten. The employees have to understand the organization, their roles & responsibilities and also adhere to the values of the company.

- 6) **Identifying and Retaining the Talent:** The biggest challenges faced by HR are the identifying and retaining the talent. In short, it is a war for talent, a war, which is being fought by the HR professional to, retained the best talented candidate in their organization.
- 7) **Compensation:** Unless the problems of compensation package and other HRM issues are handled with great care, soon there is considerable risk of a significant brain drain both domestic and international. Civil service servants, state-owned enterprise employees and others that choose not to work in these institutions will either migrate to other private and non-government organisations inside the country or flow to other countries.
- 8) **Privatisation:** Privatisation leads to a private sector business practice with a focus on quality. Privatisation is important to HRM, because it introduces modern management practices, work organization and new production technologies. There is also high possibility that firms would engage in advanced manufacturing technology, total quality management and just-in-time production. Hence, technology will shape HRM, because firms will need highly selective hiring, comprehensive training and developmental evaluation, which are absent at present. Generally, investment in different management capabilities will be required. Privatisation leads to loss of jobs in the pursuit of efficiency. It is too early to judge the overall consequences of privatisation.
- 9) **Globalization:** With the advancement and fast growth of information and communications technology (ICT), the world is becoming smaller and smaller with a speedy interaction. Globalization can have far reaching implications for HRM and management practices in general. Many countries across the globe are feeling the forces of change and they are opening up their economies (domestic markets) to external forces (influence) and at the same time penetrating other countries' economies. Accordingly, it is expected that firms will face increased competition in the domestic and international markets. Hence, firms need to transform their HRM systems in order to compete effectively in the global market. Whereas the present HRM system stress on group reward and neglect individual performance, the future of HRM policy would emphasize a

performance-based system. Performance may emerge as one of the main important variables to determine employee compensation as firms try to increase productivity. There would be a link between evaluation and reward. Therefore, performance evaluation will serve as an evaluation tool for pay increase and will be developmental in orientation. Thus, firms would shift from the current two-way and three-way performance evaluation procedures to a more objective measurement of employee performance such as the 360-degree evaluation, which include supervisors (boss), self, peers (subordinates) and customers.

- 10) **Recruiting Competent People:** With the increase of global job mobility, recruiting competent people is also increasingly becoming difficult, especially in India. Therefore organizations are also required to work out a retention strategy for the existing skilled manpower.

SUGGESTIONS

After the above study the following suggestions are noteworthy:

- 1) **Increase in Education Levels:** Due to technological progress and the spread of educational institutions workers will increasingly become aware of their higher level needs; managers will have to evolve appropriate policies and techniques to motivate the knowledge of workers. Better educated and organized workforce will demand greater discretion and autonomy at the work place.
- 2) **New Personnel Policies:** New and better polices will be required for the work force of the future. Traditional family management will give way to professional management with greater forces on human dignity
- 3) **Focus on Employee Growth and Needs:** The traditional HR only developed the policies of the organization. The present HR had to focus on employee growth, and had to be responsive to his needs and act as a bridge between the employers and the employee. Today's HR managers needed to help the employees in their wholesome growth within the organization.
- 4) **Opportunity for Talent to Mature:** Organizations need to stretch their horizons, and create time and a place for the talent to mature and grow up.

- 5) **Harnessing Energy of Youth:** The younger generation has the vision of a bigger world. They have a larger canvas. Their expectations are intense, their dreams are grand and their aspirations are unlimited. These are the realities of the youth in an uncertain and turbulent world. The youth requires harnessing of this energy and a space to encounter this reality. Organizations must channelize this energy with innovative ideas, directions and alternatives, towards a vision for tomorrow, towards a destination.
- 6) **Mobilize the Individual:** The HR's role is to mobilize the individual collectivity and the organization with a binding force of values, appropriate systems, mindsets of people, organization vision and direction, strategies and policies and above all coherence in excellence and in human processes.
- 7) **Invest Time and Amount:** It is necessary for the management to invest considerable time and amount, to learn the changing scenario of the HR department in the 21st century.
- 8) **HR Department should be updated:** In order to survive the competition and be in the race, HR department should consciously update itself with the transformation in HR and be aware of the HR issues cropping up.

TEN HUMAN RESOURCES ESSENTIALS

Looking at the present competitive environment the ten human resource essentials are:

- Establish and communicate clear ethics standards and hold managers and employees accountable
- Before hiring a new manager, assess their skills and abilities for the job. Follow up with orientation and training
- Ensure that every new employee has been sufficiently assimilated and trained
- Continue employee retention programs
- Ensure that the departments structure is aligned with overall organization's goals and strategies
- Pay attention to employee morale
- Stay ready to manage change
- Develop and implement diversity and multicultural organizational development
- Establish and communicate a solid process for managing employee performance

- Implement a recruitment process that will ensure hiring the right person

CONCLUSION

The aim of HR in the new economy is to enable the organisation to create value through people, practices and processes, bearing in mind that people are the competitive edge of any organisation. Within this context the defined role of HR must be seen as providing Human Resources products, services and solutions that will enable the organisation to achieve its set strategic objectives. Human Resources practitioners must operate as people Champions and prove their value to the organisation.

HRM departments and professionals in businesses have to take on the mandate of building a competitive HR in their respective organizations. Business survival is not only dependent on how good your product and services are, how excellent is your customer service, and how efficient your business processes are but on how competitive your employees who carry out these performances. New technology, business strategies, complicated processes, and management systems are inutile without a competent human resource behind them.

In the knowledge economies of today, success or failure of an organization depends largely on how aggressively the HR function can nourish human resource under several situations and training programs. Processes of recruitment, motivation and retention have got a new edge. Industrial relation has got a new shape in the post-global world. Innovative ideas and techniques of operations are the highly demanding attributes looked for by the corporate for its sustainability. HR is promoting the cognitive abilities in the organization to enhance the numbers of critical and analytical thinkers at all levels and, thereby, has also encouraged the accountability of the human resources for smooth functioning of the organization. In this new era, HR is playing a partnership role in the organization's strategizing business process.

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